

¹Department of Cellular and Molecular Physiology, Yale University, New Haven, CT, USA, ²Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, Princeton University, New Jersey, NJ, USA, ³University of Warwick, School of Life Sciences, United Kingdom, ⁴Laboratoire d'Ingénierie des Systèmes Macromoléculaires, Aix-Marseille Université-Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), Marseilles, France, ⁵Department of Microbiology, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, USA, ⁶Department of Molecular Biology, Princeton University, New Jersey, NJ, USA, ⁷Saints-Pères Paris Institute for the Neurosciences (SPPIN), CNRS, Paris, France. Bacterial cell division and endospore formation rely on membrane fission. In *Bacillus subtilis*, the first morphological transformation is an asymmetric division that yields a mother cell and a smaller forespore. As the mother cell membranes engulf the forespore, DNA translocation induces forespore inflation through increased turgor pressure. The *B. subtilis* protein FisB catalyzes membrane fission during sporulation, though its molecular underpinnings are unclear. Our study reveals that efficient membrane fission requires both forespore inflation and FisB accumulation at the fission site. Forespore inflation generates increased membrane tension in the engulfment membrane relative to the mother cell membrane, driving membrane flow through the connecting neck. FisB oligomerization at the neck impedes tension equilibration, further elevating engulfment membrane tension and promoting fission through lysis. These findings unveil an unanticipated role of DNA translocation in energizing FisB-mediated membrane fission under energy-restricted conditions and provide insights into the universality of fission mechanisms.

1025-FlashTalk

Bio-inspired artificial synapse with chemically mediated intercompartment communication for single-molecule cell-synthetic cell interaction studies

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Living systems do not operate in solitude, rather, intimate intercellular communication regulates and coordinates their behavior. Yet, studying cell-cell interactions is challenging due to the demands of recreating the biological membrane complexity and interfacing with biophysical measurement tools. The study of current models is usually unable to capture the dynamic intermembrane communication encountered in living cells. We present the development of an artificial double membrane system, a synapse-like architecture, comprised of an encapsulated giant unilamellar vesicle (GUV) and a droplet interface bilayer (DIB), interlinked by cholesterol-tethered DNA interactions. A DIB is formed by contacting a lipid monolayer-coated aqueous droplet with a lipid-monolayer coated hydrogel support within an oil environment. GUVs generated via electroformation or emulsion phase transfer (EPT) are included within the DIB droplet, affording compositional control of each membrane. The intermembrane DNA-mediated coupling was characterized by single molecule FRET and diffusion coefficient estimation. Chemical communication across interconnected bilayers was instigated by content exchange via alpha hemolysin (aHL) nanopores in both DIB and GUV membranes. Vesicular biochemical responses, including initiation of actin polymerisation and ionic transfer, were measured by TIRF microscopy. The method was expanded to tether individual living cells to the DIB membrane. Here, DIB-anchored integrin-targeting ligands enabled adhesion-mediated artificial membrane/live-cell interaction, creating a biohybrid system. This dual membrane system with synaptic-like intermembrane space constitutes a novel platform for studying self-organisation of mobile, paired intermembrane cleft components, intermembrane signaling, and trans-synaptic adhesion dynamics with single molecule sensitivity. Both artificial and biohybrid systems are amenable to precise compositional control and single molecule study, demonstrating the potential to interrogate fundamental membrane mediated biochemistry and multifaceted cellular responses. This will increase fundamental understanding and expand the repertoire of molecularly engineered tools for synthetic biology and biotechnology applications.

1026-FlashTalk

Osmocytosis: Osmotically induced generation and pulsatory poration of pinocytotic vesicles inside giant vesicles

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Phospholipid bilayers are dynamic components of cellular boundaries that undergo constant changes in their shapes and topology facilitating a broad

diversity of physiological functions including endo- and exocytosis, cell division, and intracellular trafficking. These shape transformations consume energy, supplied almost invariably by the activity of proteins. Here, we show that cycles of oppositely directed osmotic stresses—unassisted by protein-mediated energy supply—can induce well-defined remodeling of the bilayers of giant unilamellar vesicles, minimally recapitulating the phenomenologies of surface area homeostasis and macropinocytosis. We find that the application of a stress cycle—one consisting of deflationary hypertonic stress followed by an inflationary hypotonic one—prompts osmocytosis consisting of an elaborate sequence of membrane shape changes ultimately transporting molecular cargo from the outside into the intravesicular milieu. The initial osmotic deflation produces microscopic spherical invaginations. During the subsequent inflation, the influx of water remodels these invaginations with a bifurcated response. A sub-population contributes area to the swelling membrane thereby providing a means for surface area regulation and tensional homeostasis. The second subpopulation vesiculates into the lumens of the mother vesicles producing pinocytotic vesicles. Remarkably, the gradients of solute concentrations between the mother GUV and the daughter pinocytotic vesicles create cascades of water current, which in turn induces pulsatory transient poration enabling solute exchange between the buds and the GUV interior. The net result then is an efficient water-flux-mediated-delivery of molecular cargo across the membrane boundary. Our findings suggest a primitive physical mechanism for communication and transport across protocellular compartments driven only by osmotically propelled water activity. They also suggest plausible physical routes for intravesicular and possibly intracellular delivery of ions, solutes, and molecular cargo stimulated simply by cycles of osmotic currents of water.

1027-FlashTalk

The cortical actin cytoskeleton regulates membrane protein organization and dynamics

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The cell cytoskeleton orchestrates multiple cellular processes, including signaling, exo- and endocytosis, and mechanical stability. In particular, the cortical actin (CA) network beneath the plasma membrane interacts closely with membrane proteins, affecting their organization and dynamics. One such protein is the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), a prototypical receptor tyrosine kinase involved in cell growth and proliferation. Despite containing a putative actin-binding domain, its cytoskeletal interaction has remained elusive. In this study, we employ imaging total internal reflection-fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (ITIR-FCS) to investigate if and how the CA influences EGFR's organization and dynamics. For this purpose, we created a CA-specific probe, PMT-F-tractin, that binds to both the plasma membrane and the cytoskeleton, and used EGFR, its actin-binding domain deletion mutant (AcM-EGFR), and an EGFR-F-tractin fusion mutant to investigate the relation between EGFR and CA. As controls for the influence of CA on membrane proteins at the inner and outer leaflets, we used PMT-EGFP and GPI-EGFP, respectively. Our results show that EGFR and AcM-EGFR show similar localization and dynamics, which are only weakly correlated to CA, while those of EGFR-F-tractin show a strong correlation. In conjunction with earlier results showing that EGFR dynamics are actin-dependent, this implies that the impact of cortical actin on EGFR operates indirectly. Similar findings were observed with PMT-EGFP and GPI-EGFP, both of which do not directly bind to actin. These results indicate that the CA has an overall influence on membrane structure that regulates the organization and dynamics of membrane proteins. This regulation is independent of the proteins' locations and operates via steric interactions (PMT-EGFP), indirect patterning of lipid domains through protein interactions (GPI-EGFP), or a combination of both mechanisms (EGFR-mEGFP).

Platform: Motor Proteins and Cytoskeletal Assemblies II

1028-Plat

Structural basis for recognition of the cargo adapter Rab6^{GTP} by the dynein adapter BicD2

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Rab6 is a key modulator of protein secretion. The dynein adapter Bicaudal D2 (BicD2) recruits the motors dynein and kinesin-1 to Rab6^{GTP}-positive vesicles